

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LONG DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	12	04	BUENOS AIRES	S 34°	36.22332	W 58°	22.89552
End	2021	12	27	USHUAIA	S 54°	48.577	W 68°	18.034

CAMPAIGN OBJECTIVE

The Tara MM Gayoso experiment: A holistic study of coccolithophore bloom dynamics.

Every spring, the Patagonian shelf and shelf-break experience massive phytoplankton blooms. While diatoms and dinoflagellates dominate at the beginning, gigantic patches of high reflectance waters associated with coccolithophores are detected towards December. These develop in long (100-1000 km) south-to-north streaks along the shelf-break for several weeks, on the track of the strong, northward-flowing Malvinas Current. Whether the bloom is only advected or also benefits from upwellings and therefore fertilization processes triggered by the current along the shelf break is currently not known.

Our specific questions are: (a) What are the ecosystem dynamics of a coccolithophore bloom and demise? (b) What are the contributions of different mortality agents (viruses, bacteria, allelopathy, grazers) in the bloom's demise and its metabolic footprint? (c) What is the role of infochemicals as mediators (notably through vesicles) of microbial interactions? (d) What are the large-scale biogeochemical consequences of microbial interactions? (e) Which type of microorganisms, viruses, and bacteria are emitted from coccolithophore blooms? (f) How does the Patagonian bloom relate to global coccolithophore biology?

To address these questions, we deployed a unique sampling plan in a joint effort with a local Argentinian consortium. In November 2021, the mythical sailing boat 'Motovelero Bernardo Houssay' applied the AtlantEco multi-omics protocol to assess the early stages of the bloom from Ushuaia to Buenos Aires. The 'Houssay' met 'Tara' in Buenos Aires, and Tara performed in December 2021 a Lagrangian drift on a coccolithophore patch, guided by satellite data and SVP drifters, and deploying to our knowledge the most advanced eco-systemic protocols ever applied to a natural plankton bloom. This included, beyond the meta-omics (meta-B/G/T) samples, new protocols to assess the extracellular vesicles, single cell transcriptomics, the meta-proteome and meta-metabolome, the surface micro layer, a suite of specific methods targeting lipid- and gene-based molecular biomarkers of coccolithophores and their viruses, together with in-situ continuous measurements using optical sensors. **This campaign summary report focuses on the Tara leg.**

PARTICIPANTS

	ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	AUDRAIN, Samuel
2	CREW - 1st Officer	BIN, Nicolas
3	CREW – Chief engineer	BOULON, Léo
4	CREW – Deck officer	PRIEUR, Alain
5	CREW – Deck officer	ORIENT, Matthieu
6	CREW - Cook	PIRE, Carole

7	CREW – Media	LEROUX, Marin
8	GUEST - Artist	BERTIN, Antoine
9	GUEST	
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	BOURDIN, Guillaume
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab Metabolomics	KUHLISCH, Constanze
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab Genomics	FLORES, Michel
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab Biogeochemistry	RATIN, Morgane
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab Sorting/imaging	SILVA, Ricardo
15	SCIENCE - F - Chief Scientist	VINCENT, Flora

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

Chlorophyll map over 17 days, with inline. We observe a big phytoplankton bloom along the shelf break. (plotted by Guillaume Bourdin)

bbp550 map over 17 days, with inline. We observe a big bbp550 signal bloom along the shelf break and the Malvinas. bbp550 capture coccolithophores but also general phytoplankton. (plotted by Guillaume Bourdin)

bbp550/chl map over 17 days, with inline. This ratio enables us to target blooms that are enriched in coccolithophores. This seems to have been a relevant strategy as our cell concentrations were similar to typical Balch transects. Focusing only on bbp550 or PIC can be misleading but will most likely depends on the biological question. bbp or PIC can be more relevant when we target "high concentration" but could be accompanied by many other species, whereas bbp/Chl seems to favour coccolithophore enrichment. (plotted by Guillaume Bourdin)

PIC Modis 8Days with scale (plotted by Louis Marié)

PIC Modis 8Days with Tara stations (plotted by Flora Vincent with Remi Laxenaire system)

One week before departure:

The day of the departure 04/12:

First 2 stations A059 and A060: (not too bad!)

The week of the Lagrangian 11/12-19/12:

Below, the week post lagrangian: This long streak visible West of the Lagrangian may not be Coccolithophores, and the inline will help us decipher it. Ultimately, **good true color pictures** will also be helpful for this. 18/12-26-12 correspond to the last three stations.

Following week picture:

Bathymetry (plotted by Flora Vincent)

Drifters (plotted by Loreley Lago & Martin Saraceno)

Lagrangian 2 - Drifter 3

Lagrangian 2 - Drifter 5

TS PLOT (Plotted by Guillaume Bourdin)

Zoom in on the Lagrangian. Careful, different rosette are not indicated here.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

(highlight how this particular campaign may differ from other campaigns)

One of the major goals of this scientific leg was to target a coccolithophore bloom. Despite being a massive phenomenon visible from space, it remains challenging to track in real time the onset of the bloom on such a wide area. Moreover, while backscattering (and the corresponding modelled PIC) are considered to be good indicators of coccolithophores, they are generally associated with bloom demise. Given our intentions to follow the bloom dynamics, catching early phases of the bloom forced to not only focus on high PIC but also low PIC regions. **A major achievement was to repeatedly sample waters with high coccolithophore concentrations** based on the combination of satellite imagery providing broad spatial coverage, a recently developed hyper-spectral inline backscattering sensor measuring the surface water providing high temporal resolution, and flow cytometry allowing to assess coccolithophore abundances due to the specificity of their high cell side scattering.

A second important objective of the leg was to perform a Lagrangian drift, namely to follow the same water mass thanks to drifting buoys that served as an anchor in the water mass. The Lagrangian drift was separated in two phases, from A061-A063 (located on the eastern side of the main Malvinas jet) with moderate *E. huxleyi* abundances (<1000 cells/mL), and A064-A067 located around 20 nautical miles eastwards - in a low current area between two jets - with high *E. huxleyi* abundances (>1000 cells/mL). A relocation was done on the night between 14th and 15th of December, combining inline measurements analysis, flow cytometry measurements, and SVP release. **Performing a Lagrangian drift for seven consecutive days in the edge and centre of a coccolithophore bloom is a major achievement, that will significantly facilitate our data interpretation and knowledge on bloom development in the natural environment.** An important additional aspect in that regard is the fruitful liaison between scientists and sailors to reach the two above-mentioned goals of this leg. The trajectory of this leg was assessed and adjusted daily based on bloom development and the weather conditions in the region. This was accomplished by the constructive interaction between the scientific and the sailing crew to aim for the most efficient manoeuvring in response to the coccolithophore bloom development.

Thanks to the very well thought scientific platforms installed on Tara, the Gayoso team was able to introduce and perform novel protocols that are not part of the AtlantEco package and that were

overall never performed on Tara. The versatile equipment available enabled us to setup grazing assays, single cell RNA sequencing protocols, TEP sampling as well as DOM. **A major achievement was thus the complementary installation of topic-specific protocols besides the AtlantEco protocols for a broad and ecologically relevant sampling.**

Of scientific interest is the **overall use the optical properties of coccolithophores to detect them from space and in situ:**

- Via satellite (for detail ask G. Bourdin)
 - Using G. Bourdin bbp550nm: this is **modelled** particle back scattering from a ratio of reflectance and targets the green wavelength to 1) be able to compare it with the onboard inline system and 2) avoid too much absorption from chlorophyll. Those images use a composite of several satellites thus do not contain a lot of clouds. However bbp550nm is not specific to coccolithophores.
 - Using NASA PIC model: PIC is **modelled** from the bb546nm, itself derived from a ratio of irradiance and under the assumption that only calcium carbonate can get into bb546nm (subject to debate)
- On the CTD Rosette: the VSF measuring scattering in one angle or bbp (124 degrees)
- Inline system: bb550nm = **real measurement** of bbp
- Accuri (for detail ask F. Vincent): the only device that gives actual **cell concentration** of coccolithophores

A few scientific thoughts that emerged/summarised during the leg:

- Targeting High PIC (or bbp)/ChlA ratios on satellite imaging could privilege *E. huxleyi* enriched regions on top of individual PIC and ChlA analysis. Always keep in mind the absolute values of PIC and ChlA and how they influence the ratio between both.
- The bbp/ChlA ratio could also be a proxy for the bloom state with higher bbp/chla in demise phase
- According to local expert Valeria Guinder, coccolithophores on the shelf are likely other species like *Gephyrocapsa*, whereas coccolithophores on the shelf break would most likely be *E. huxleyi* (Valeria)
- Surface chlorophyll by other phytoplankton can « mask » deep coccolithophores in satellite imaging: a low satellite PIC value does not mean no *E. huxleyi*
- Coccolithophores on the outer shelf break were more abundant in the north (3000 cells/mL), maybe also because the water was more stratified (see following point)
- The water column was very stratified in the northern sampling stations (<45°S), so coccolithophores were concentrated at one depth in high abundances. In the southern stations (>45°S) the upper 20 meter were highly mixed: could this dilute the population leading to lower abundances but higher (or equivalent) integrated biomass?
- High PIC seen from satellite can mean high coccolithophores concentration in the deep, or low coccolithophores in the surface
- Only genetics and morpho (SEM) will tell us if we sampled *E. huxleyi*; our approach was more a “coccolithophore hunt” than a “*E. huxleyi* hunt” – for the future, benchtop SEM (\$50-80K, ~size of a desktop PC)
- Having access to remote sensing maps on board together with the inline bbp sensor is critical for such a hunt. The speed at which we need to take decision on **where** to go forces us to reach the highest possible autonomy.

- Remember that the inline samples the surface. We still have no idea of how surface concentration reflects deeper waters => a big surface screening coupled with deep sampling would be amazing. In general, more SRF + DCM sampling would be nice.
- We were lacking depth resolution – to improve the next Lagrangian experiment: possible to integrate the bbp sensor into the TIA and attach it to one SVP drifter that is recovered in the end?
- On A069 could it be another species of coccolithophores?
- In the future, we could use gliders or drones to target the region a bit better. Samples in a star-like manner from the boat to better locate the bloom

A few logistic thoughts that emerged during the leg:

- While there were concerns in the beginning about a long consecutive sampling strategy, it was possible to sample seven days in a row by alternating between long and short days and beforehand prepared consumables for all days without reaching exhaustion level of the crew
- We can think about a gradual type of expedition: small priority protocols to focus on for the first station, but adding more and more. The first station was clearly a mess, with half of the Gayoso that could not happen. Towards the end, we could add one rosette for a targeted TEP depth profile for example.
- We should think of an organized recovery of SVP drifters (we recovered one easily at the end of the drift) including higher reliability of GPS signals (we lost three SVPs). Sailors saw it as highly incoherent to dump SVP **without even thinking of recovery** while defending ocean protection.
- Time is the main constraint that forces the use of engine when not necessary.
- Inventory is not perfect, e.g. while there were several boxes of XL and S gloves, there were no L and only two boxes of M left for the leg
- Could we consider night time sampling? We are biasing to daytime measurements and there are more and more evidence of the diurnal oscillations of phytoplankton.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Provide overview of sampling activities during the Campaign.

Station ###	Date (Z=UTC) YYYYMMDDZ	Latitude	Longitude	Depth(s)	Station type	CAST – Z00-Z10	CAST – EHM - Conny	NET – WP11 200	CAST – EHM - BGC	NET – WP11 20	VMP	Bow Pole	Microtops	hTSRB	CAST – EHM - Gayoso	CAST – EHM - Atlanteco	NET – Régent 680	NET – Régent 680	Grazing	TIA	SVP Release	Underway
-	20211205:2321	S 37°37.878	W 56°05.193	-	-								X							X		X
-	20211206:1946	S 39°13.662	W 55°53.359	-	-								4X							X		X
A059	20211207:0936	S 40°23.539	W 55°40.483	EHM	G-f	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
A060	20211209:0924	S 42°14.168	W 57°13.984	EHM	G-f	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X				
-	20211210:1220	S 43°28.149	W 56°37.238	-									X									X
-	20211211:1810			-	-																	X
A061	20211212:1023	S 45°56.333	W 59°34.918	EHM	G-f	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X	
A062	20211213:1040	S 45°38.388	W 59°32.781	EHM	G-h	X	X			X			X	X	X							
A063	20211214:0927	S 45°23.609	W 59°38.355	EHM	G-f	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X			X
A064	20211215:1121	S 45°14.620	W 59°09.994	EHM	G-h	X	X			X					X						X	
A065	20211216:1004	S 44°59.574	W 59°15.187	EHM	G-f	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X			X
A066	20211217:0917	S 44°45.737	W 59°19.535	EHM	G-h	X	X			X	X			X	X							
A067	20211218:0907	S 44°29.280	W 59°14.869	EHM	G-h	X	X			X		X			X				X			X
A068	20211221:1038	S 49°11.819	W 64°00.512	SRF DCM	A	X	X	X	X	X		X				X	X	X				
A069	20211223:0914	S 51°55.329	W 65°02.570	EHM	G-f	X	X	X	X	X		X		X	X	X	X	X	X			
A070	20211224:0913	S 53°38.671	W 65°40.930	SRF	G-f	X	X	X	X	X		X			X	X	X	X				

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING HALF STATIONS

Storage T°C

Box size

Chemical

10	4	-20	-80	-80	-80
			#1	#2	#3

Protocol	Container type						
HP	2-mL-cryotube					5	
NU	20-mL-vial			10			
S20	5-mL-cryotube				1		
S20-L	5-mL-falcon			1			
E20	15-mL-falcon			1			
FM20	50-mL-falcon		1				
MB20	4-mL-vial			1			
CP20	ziplock	1					
PM20	ziplock	1					
AS	2-mL-cryotube						1
AI	47mm petri slide	1					
AF	Whirlpack			1			
SSML	2-mL-cryotube						3
SML-FC-G	2-mL-cryotube						3
SML-TOC	30ml-vial			6			
gVLT	2-mL-cryotube					10	
gB320	5-mL-cryotube				7		
gB023	5-mL-cryotube				7		
gB<02	5-mL-cryotube		2				
gMB<02	50-mL-falcon			1			
gMB<02-ac	50-mL-falcon			1			
gMBGFC	50-mL-falcon			2			
gMB045	15-mL-falcon			2			
gPOM	Zip-lock			2			
gDOM	20-mL-glass-vial			1			
gSEM	petri-slide	1					
gCCO	Zip-lock			1			
gVES	50-mL-falcon	1					
gPIS	50-mL-falcon	1					

gTIS	15-mL-falcon	1					
gSCT	2-mL-cryotube			2			
gNUT	15-mL-falcon			1			
gALK	15-mL-falcon			1			
gBFISH	petri-slide			1			
gVIS	15-mL-falcon		1				
gTEP	2-mL-cryotube			8			
gBIS	2-mL-cryotube					2	
gSCTBD	2-mL-cryotube					1	
iFCM							21

ONE HALF STATION	7	4	43	15	18	28
4 HALF STATION	28	16	172	60	72	112

SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING FULL STATIONS

Storage T°C

Box size

Chemical

10	4	-20	-80 #1	-80 #2	-80 #3
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Protocol

Container type

HP	2-mL-cryotube				8	
PM	aluminium	1				
eDNA	sterivex			1		
DICTA	500-mL-bottle	1				
DINO	60-mL-bottle			2		
MTE-T	125-mL-bottle	1				
MB023	4-mL-vial			1		
MB<02	50-mL-falcon			1		
MB320	4-mL-vial			1		
DGAS	ExeV-12mL		3			
SAL	125-mL-bottle	1				
NU	20-mL-vial			10		
S20	5-mL-cryotube				1	
S20-L	5-mL-falcon			1		
E20	15-mL-falcon			1		
FM20	50-mL-falcon		1			
S200-L	5-mL-falcon			1		
S200	5-mL-cryotube				1	

E200	15-mL-falcon			1		
F200	250-mL-bottle	1				
MB20	4-mL-vial			1		
MB200	4-mL-vial			1		
CP20	ziplock	1				
PM200	ziplock	1				
PM20	ziplock	1				
S680-L	5-mL-falcon			1		
S680	petri-plates					
E680	50-mL-falcon			1		
F680	250-mL-bottle	1				
E2000	15-mL-falcon			1		
HG	125-mL-bottle	1				
EM	petri-slide	1				
SG	5-mL-cryotube				3	
HC	2-mL-cryotube					4
FC	2-mL-cryotube					9
AS	2-mL-cryotube					1
AI	47mm petri slide	1				
AF	Whirlpack			1		
SSML	2-mL-cryotube					1
SML-FC-G	2-mL-cryotube					1
SML-TOC	30ml-vial			2		
S025-L	15-mL-falcon			1		
S520-L	5-mL-falcon			1		
FM5	50-mL-falcon		2			
P320	5-mL-cryotube				1	
P023	5-mL-cryotube				1	
S320	5-mL-cryotube				3	
S023	5-mL-cryotube				3	
S<02	5-mL-cryotube		3			
gVLT	2-mL-cryotube					10
gB320	5-mL-cryotube				7	
gB023	5-mL-cryotube				7	
gB<02	5-mL-cryotube		2			
gMB<02	50-mL-falcon			1		
gMB<02-ac	50-mL-falcon			1		
gMBGFC	50-mL-falcon			2		

gMB045	15-mL-falcon			2			
gPOM	Zip-lock			2			
gDOM	20-mL-glass-vial			1			
gSEM	petri-slide	1					
gCCO	Zip-lock			1			
gVES	50-mL-falcon	1					
gPIS	50-mL-falcon	A1 (no shipping)					
gTIS	15-mL-falcon	A1 (no shipping)					
gSCT	2-mL-cryotube			2			
gNUT	15-mL-falcon			1			
gALK	15-mL-falcon			1			
gBFISH	petri-slide			1			
gVIS	15-mL-falcon		1				
gTEP	2-mL-cryotube			8			
gBIS	2-mL-cryotube					2	
gSCTBD	2-mL-cryotube					1	
iFCM	2-mL-cryotube						21

1 FULL STATION		14	12	53	27	25	33
7 FULL STATION		98	84	371	189	175	231
4 HALF STATION		28	16	172	60	72	112

TOTAL LEG 10		126	100	543	249	247	285
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Need to add the equivalent of 1 AtlantEco station (SRF + DCM)